
The Role of Social-Psychological Factors in the Adoption of Push-Pull Technology By Smallholder Farmers across East Africa: Application of the Theory of Planned Behavior

Sunday, August 4, 2024

11:40 AM - 12:00 PM

N3 (Ground Floor, NASC Complex Office Block)

Abstract

Push-pull technology (PPT) continues to gain relevance among smallholder farmers across the East African region in dealing with constraints affecting cereal crop yields including stemborers, fall armyworm, *Striga* weed, and low soil fertility. While previous research has emphasized the significance of farmers' socioeconomic factors in explaining farmers' decisions to adopt PPT, the socio-psychological factors that influence the intention to adopt the technology have not been extensively studied. Therefore, this study examined the influence of these factors on the intention to adopt PPT based on the theory of planned behavior (TPB). A total of 971 farmers comprising PPT users and non-users were interviewed in Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, and Rwanda using a structured questionnaire. Utilizing the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN), this study revealed that the TPB constructs, and the additional construct "Perceived Limitations" have a significant impact on farmers' intentions to adopt PPT. The results from both models revealed that subjective norm serves as the primary determinant of farmers' intentions to adopt PPT. These findings emphasize the importance of socio-psychological factors in PPT adoption, providing valuable insights for policymakers to promote and enhance the adoption of the technology across the region.

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